

Plant-based

Fermentation

Cultivated

EU alternative protein R&I ecosystem

Alternative proteins – plant-based, fermentation-derived or cultivated – offer a promising solution to meet the projected growth in the global demand for meat, seafood, eggs, and dairy, while building a more sustainable food system.

3,221 publications

+33% average annual growth
+306% from 2020 to 2025

5,366 patents

+940% from 2015 to 2025

+213% funding

from 2020 to 2025 in alternative protein R&I

If the EU makes alternative proteins a strategic priority, the sector could contribute significantly to the bloc's economy by 2040.

€111B
annual economic contribution

+400,000
jobs supported